

PRIN 2022 RESIST

DELIVERABLE 2000-A

30-01-2024

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the industrial landscape has been observed a unique surge in digitalization and connectivity, leading in the era of Industry 4.0 by improving operations and functionality, but driving systems towards increasing complexity to manage the new challenge and innovation in the processes (Baxter & Sommerville, 2011; Righi & Saurin, 2015). This transformation is characterized by the integration of advanced technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and grownup computing systems, into the industrial processes. The principles of Industry 4.0 have become pervasive in the present industrial sectors, finding adoption among virtually every competitive organization worldwide. A tangible manifestation of this transformation lies in the increasing prevalence of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) (Drozdov et al., 2017). These integrative systems comprise interconnected computing and control devices that interact seamlessly with the physical infrastructure or organizational framework through sensors and actuators. A distinguishing feature of CPSs is their capacity to continuously engage with the physical systems they operate within, wielding the competence to compute, communicate, and control the surrounding physical conditions or environments. A rapid increase in the use of CPSs occurred in recent years ranging from smart grids to smart factories, Industrial Control Systems (ICS), and automation-robotics (Patriarca et al., 2021a). However, this integration of advanced technologies, while delivering elevated effectiveness, improved coordination, and enhanced overall quality, has given rise to the novel classification of Cyber-Socio-Technical Systems (CSTSs) (De Nicola et al., 2023). To clarify this definition, it is worth reporting that: (i) traditional technical systems refer to physical devices, infrastructures, and machines, which are used to support human activities; and (ii) socio-technical systems deal mainly with the above-mentioned symbiotic interactions between physical systems and human agents. However, as discussed above, modern technical systems are defined by both a cyber and a physical part. The former encompasses software systems, which nowadays are characterized by increasing autonomy and intelligence, while the latter includes traditional technical systems, hardware infrastructures, and other modern physical devices, such as sensors and actuators, which are meant to interoperate with their cyber counterpart. In this report, the notion of CSTS is used to emphasize that the analysis includes those systems that deal with cyber artefacts, physical devices, and human agents together. The CSTSs underscore the intricate interplay among cyber-technical artifacts, humans, and organizations, recognizing the synergies that unfold over time in these modern systems and the interactions among the system elements into the process. On the other hand, the CSTSs lead to a series of completely new disruption scenarios with a potential disastrous impact.

In an increasingly complex and highly dynamical industrial scenario, safety and risk management approaches, that traditionally deal with disruptive events trying to reduce both their probability of occurrence and their impact, demand for reconsideration (Hollnagel, 2012). The goal of secure and safer systems, which have been usually achieved through risk mitigation in the form of prevention and protection, is still challenging. Even if these strategies are critical to prevent extremely negative consequences, recent advancements in the field of safety and security management suggest that not all the occurrences of undesired events can be prevented nor adequately controlled (Leveson, 2011). As the industrial landscape embraces the benefits of Industry 4.0 or even Industry 5.0, and the seamless integration of CPSs into operational frameworks, a parallel reality emerges one fraught with challenges and security concerns (Banks & Stanton, 2019).

This technical report delves into the intricacies of CPSs, especially considering their socio-technical nature as CSTSs, shedding light on their evolution, applications, and the critical need for cybersecurity measures and safety constraints. It is within this context that cybersecurity is not

confined to conventional data or information hacking; instead, it extends its reach to potential modifications of physical processes, raising alarms about tangible damage, losses, and breakages. This report aims to explore and address these challenges, offering insights into the delicate balance required to secure the future of industrial systems in the age of Industry 5.0. Therefore, the current study covers the three main approaches emerged from a review of current literature (i.e., control theory, resilience, and information flow modelling) without restrictions on their application and scope domains by including different variables (e.g., modelling approach, type of the system, and industry sectors studied) as fully detailed in the following sections.

The obtained results have been inspired by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) framework (Moher et al., 2009) to support the execution of the scoping review on available state of the art on the CSTSs modelling in the industrial settings.

2. METHODOLOGY

The PRISMA framework provides guidelines for reporting systematic reviews, as per the following core steps:

1. **Definition and aims of the review:** to develop a systematic review it is necessary to define some features to identify the research question and the criteria of selection to analyze the documentation. For this reason, the following features allow to define the aims of scope:
 - Research question to ensure a specific, measurable, and relevant content for the analysis.
 - Criteria of selection outlining the review process. Include criteria for study inclusion/exclusion, search strategies, data extraction, and statistical analysis plan.
 - Academic databases search engine to conduct a comprehensive literature search using academic databases to identify and extract the data document in terms of inclusion and exclusion criteria.
2. **Study and data selection:** to allow the screening of the documents to be analyzed. Then, from the documents, relevant data will be extracted from selected studies using a standardized form.
3. **Eligibility documentation:** to evaluate the representativeness of each included study.
4. **Analysis of the documentation:** to synthesize the elected documents, employing either narrative synthesis or bibliometric synthesis.

The PRISMA framework has been selected as it ensures transparency and completeness in reporting reviews, enhancing the reliability and usability of the research. Moreover, opting for a scoping review has been deemed appropriate to assess the extent of a topic's coverage in the literature and provide dependable insights into the quantity, nature, and other attributes of relevant publications (Munn et al., 2018).

3. RESULTS

This section shows the literature review results, paired with a step-by-step explanation of the PRISMA relevant phases.

3.1. Definition and aims of the review

The research question has been defined as:

“In the context of CPSs within the broader of CSTSs, how, and to which extent, do modelling techniques integrate socio-technical aspects and human-machine interactions to enhance the safety and security of interconnected industrial systems and coupled industrial processes?”

In particular, the research question has been translated into a query to be used in Scopus search engine for the exploration and extraction of the documents. Then, the query was:

“TITLE-ABS-KEY ("cyber" AND "model" AND ("socio* technical" OR "*man*machine*")”*

The criteria of the analysis have been defined in the following Table 1:

Table 1 – Inclusion and exclusion criteria

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Inclusion</i>	<i>Exclusion</i>
Language	The analysis considered the documents only written in the English language	The documents written other than English
Type of the document	Journal manuscripts and Conference proceedings	Chapters books, Technical reports, Books, Whitepapers, Academic Theses, Lectures or Notes
Scope	Publications presenting research or non-empirical work on CSTSs modelling	Publication on focused in the CSTSs modelling
Document availability	Full-text available or retrievable by the resources available at any of the project partners	Documents in which the full-text is not obtained

3.2. Study selection and data extraction

The query returned 183 documents matching the query search criteria. During the screening process 106 documents have been marked out of scope since they are not compliant with the inclusion. Table 2 describes the documents excluded and the reason for exclusion. For instance, since the scoping review proposed here aims to investigate empirical research, 13 documents have been excluded being literature reviews, and 20 being conference proceedings summaries. In addition, a set of 52 documents have been excluded since they are out of the application approach, i.e., organizational modelling, human factor and cognitive modelling and circular economy and sustainability applications, terrorists attack through social networks data, competence engineering analysis in industry 4.0, humanoids application, augmented reality simulation, cyber-crime and digital forensic, computer science application, e.g., software developing, security policies, and computer modelling, agriculture applications, and maturity models analyses. Finally, 21 documents have been excluded from the analysis on the grounds that they are not written in English or fall into any of the following categories: books, book series, editorials, industrial reports, or academic theses.

Table 2 – Number of documents excluded in the analysis

<i>Motivation of exclusion</i>	<i>Number of documents</i>
Out of dominion	73
Conference proceeding summary	20
Literature review	13

Finally, this filtering process led to the inclusion of 77 documents in the next step of the analysis. These documents represents the 72% of the total.

3.3. Eligibility process

This round of review allowed a refinement of the paper sample, by removing those articles that afforded highly diverse interpretations, or they were not aligned with the scope of the research: (i) 8 of them afforded highly diverse interpretations or they are not aligned with the scope of the research (discrepancy between the title, abstract and keywords and the whole paper), and (ii) the remaining 12 documents have not been available as full-text in the database. Then, the result of this process led to 57 documents to be proposed in the next stages of the analysis.

3.4. Analysis of the documentation

From the full-text reading of the selected contribution, three major streams of research emerged:

- *Resilience engineering modelling.* Some research works focuses on the study of the CSTS performance. They pinpoint that the main goal of the CSTS is to preserve an acceptable performance despite what adverse scenarios could verify, embracing the resilience perspective that it is important to evaluate the ability of the system to withstand, to adapt and to recover from any unexpected event As such, the focus is on modelling systems' operational performance by means of tasks agents perform, giving major emphasis on how these tasks

influence each other. There is no specific focus on agents themselves, but operations and related performance represent the central point of these type of modelling approaches.

- *Control theory modelling.* A common approach rely on modelling the CSTS adopting a control theory-inspired perspective. As such, agents within the system are studied pointing at how agents decide to modify the operations of others, and what data agents communicate to make these decisions possible. Such methods give a clear systemic representation of the interactions between elements of the CSTS as a control action/feedback exchange.
- *Information flow modelling.* The third approach focuses on the information exchange within the CSTS. As such, these models distinguish the process stages within the process to then describe how information flows through the system. These modelling approaches characterize the kinds of data that flow through the process, capturing how and who could access them. In this perspective, the massive data exchange in the CSTS fosters the understanding of its complexity.

This general overview on the adopted modelling approach (e.g., control theory modelling, resilience engineering modelling, and information flow modelling), enables the representation of the distribution of publications per system type (i.e., technical/cyber, socio, technical/physical, cyber physical, socio-technical, and cyber-socio-technical) and per modelling approach. Accordingly, Table 3 shows the number of documents retrieved after the screening, divided by modelling approach. In which, 54,38% of the papers are related to control theory modelling (31 documents out of 57), the almost remaining 45,00% are related to resilience engineering modelling (24,56%; 14 documents out of 57) and to information flow modelling (21,05%; 12 documents out of 57).

Table 3 – Distribution of the documents by modelling approach

<i>Modelling approach</i>	<i>Number of documents after screening</i>
Control Theory modelling	31
Resilience Engineering modelling	14
Information Flow modelling	12

Table 4 – Distribution of the documents by modelling approach

<i>System type</i>	<i>Number of documents</i>
Cyber-Physical	27
Cyber-Socio-Technical	22
Socio-Technical	6
Technical/Cyber	1
Social	1
Technical/Physical	0

In addition, Figure 1 visually represents the same information, i.e. the distribution of the selected paper for the review by the modeling approach used.

Out of the 57 papers, almost 47,37% present a cyber-physical investigation as system type (27 documents of 57); 38,6% of the articles regarded with the CSTSs (22 documents of 57), the remaining papers represent around the 12% of the paper considered in the analysis. Therefore, Table 4 depicts the number of papers by the type of system modelled.

In addition, Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of research papers across three axes corresponding to the technical/cyber, social, and technical/physical aspects. In particular, the socio-technical papers are almost double-counted, contributing to both the social and technical features. The analysis reveals a uniform distribution of coverage across the three aspects for all modeling approaches. No modeling paradigm exhibits a pronounced emphasis on a specific aspect. However, it is significant that the field of control theory has a marginally higher number of associated papers.

Figure 1. Distribution of the documents after the application of the screening criteria

Figure 2. System type analysis by social, technical/physical and technical/cyber analysis in the investigation of the review

Regarding the domain or context in which the investigation has been performed, it is possible to highlight that industrial processes could be considered as the common domain application in this review (ca. 43,85% of the papers) following by other IT application (about 15%). Hence, Figure 3 depicts the number of papers by domain of application. In addition, the analysis has been performed by modelling approach to divide and analyze further the approach used by domain of application.

Through a systematic analysis of all the eligible documents, the previous section presents a quantitative examination of relevant features such as the system type, domain of analysis and application, for control theory, resilience engineering and information flows as domains to model the CSTSs. The bibliometric findings from the contributions are discussed to critically how the CSTSs in the present are managed and analyzed giving a comprehensive picture of the research field.

Furthermore, to summarize the results of the literature review, the following sections describe the most relevant documents highlighting how they fit in the scope of this review, in terms of methodologies, domain and system type have been crucial for the investigation.

Figure 3. Number of papers by modelling approach, classified by domain of application

3.4.1. Manuscripts related with the resilience engineering modelling

This section describes and summarizes the most relevant papers related to resilience engineering modelling techniques, as reported in Table 5.

Table 5 – Summary table of the most relevant paper related to resilience engineering modelling

Citation	Title and summary of the paper	Domain of application
(Masys et al., 2016)	<i>'Black Swans', 'Dragon Kings' and Beyond: Towards Predictability and Suppression of Extreme All-Hazards Events Through Modeling and Simulation</i> The paper explores the predictability and suppression of extreme events, termed 'Black Swans' and 'Dragon Kings,' which pose significant threats to global systems. The study emphasizes the importance of modeling and simulation in understanding and mitigating the impacts of low-probability, high-consequence events such as natural disasters, cyber-attacks, and financial crises.	Others
(Håring et al., 2017)	<i>Towards a generic resilience management, quantification and development process: General definitions, requirements, methods, techniques and measures, and case studies</i> This work delves into a comprehensive resilience framework and management process that transcends generic risk management and functional safety standards. The proposed framework covers cyber-physical socio-technical systems, non-	Industrial operations

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	linear system behavior, and various dimensions of security. The work contributes to the development of credible certification for critical infrastructure and safety-critical systems.	
(Patriarca et al., 2021)	<i>WAX: An integrated conceptual framework for the analysis of cyber-socio-technical systems</i> This paper examines knowledge dynamics in cyber-socio-technical systems (CSTSs), focusing on modern work domains' intricate interplay between social and technical elements. The proposed Work-As-x (WAX) framework reveals relationships in different work representations and agents. Emphasizing systemic research, the framework encourages a shift from reductionist approaches, fostering a deeper understanding of interactions and adaptation in evolving work ecosystems, promoting organizational resilience and learning.	Industrial operations
(Colabianchi et al., 2023)	<i>MARLIN Method: Enhancing Warehouse Resilience in Response to Disruptions</i> This study introduces the MARLIN (Method wArehouse ResILience dIstruptionN), rooted in resilience engineering, to enhance warehouse adaptability during disruptive events. Empirical testing in an Italian warehouse validates MARLIN's effectiveness in identifying areas requiring intervention and associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).	Industrial operations – Warehouse
(Köpke et al., 2020)	<i>Security and resilience for airport infrastructure</i> This paper delves into airport security, focusing on vulnerabilities to combined cyber-physical threats in the context of the EU-H2020 project SATIE. Employing Agent-Based Modeling, the simulation tool represents not only technical aspects but also the social dimension of airport systems, particularly passenger interactions. The paper acknowledges the tool's current limitations, emphasizing its potential for improved threat analysis and mitigation in airport security.	Aviation
(Fairburn et al., 2021)	<i>Beyond Murphy's Law: Applying Wider Human Factors Behavioural Science Approaches in Cyber-Security Resilience: An Applied Practice Case Study Discussing Approaches to Assessing Human Factors Vulnerabilities in Cyber-Security Systems</i> The paper discusses approaches to cyber-security resilience arguing that in complex socio-technical systems, human behavior are important aspects to be considered. As such, authors pointed at Human Factor disciplines to be necessary to deal with the problem of cyber-security resilience. The study's major finding is that among all methods, the most effective are the ones considering cultural factors.	Others - Theoretical
(De Nicola et al., 2023)	<i>Development and measurement of a resilience indicator for cyber-socio-technical systems: The allostatic load</i> The authors propose the concept of allostatic load, which is a measure that considers the repeated adaptation to stressors, to assess complex systems resilience. The methodology involves the use of semantic technologies, the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM), the WAX conceptual framework, and a crowd-based approach to elicit industrial knowledge. The authors validate their approach with two real case studies.	Industrial operations - Pharma and aluminum
(Perozzo et al., 2022)	<i>CyberSecurity Readiness: A Model for SMEs based on the Socio-Technical Perspective</i>	Others

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	The authors propose a CyberSecurity Readiness Model for SMEs (namely, CSRSM-SME) based on a Socio-Technical view of the organization. The model enables a further understanding of the strategies adopted by the SMEs to prevent and manage cyber-attacks. The CSRSM-SME model provides a comprehensive framework for assessing cybersecurity readiness in SMEs, offering valuable insights into the strategies and environments that can help prevent and manage cyber-attacks.	
(Grøtan et al., 2020)	<i>Secure Safety; State-of-the-art and remaining challenges</i> The paper discusses the concept of Secure Safety in the context of Safety Instrumented Systems in the oil and gas industry. The authors argue that there is the need to extend Secure Safety approach with the resilience concept. The paper explores the challenges of adopting a resilience perspective to an increasingly software-intensive domain. Authors also provide a roadmap for future work on SeSa resilience.	Industrial operations – Oil and Gas

3.4.2. Manuscripts related with the control theory modelling

This section describes and summarizes the most relevant papers related to the control theory modelling techniques, as reported in Table 6.

Table 6 – . Summary table of the most relevant paper related to control theory modelling

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
(Zoto et al., 2018)	<i>Using a socio-technical systems approach to design and support systems thinking in cyber security education</i> The focus of the research is on addressing the gap between companies and institutions planned Information Security policies and the system perspective required for an effective implementation. The researchers advocate for an STS approach, emphasizing systems thinking in cybersecurity education. The crucial finding is a change in the perceived relevance of defense attributes, emphasizing the impact of motivation over resources.	Others – Education
(Al Sabbagh & Kowalski, 2012)	<i>ST(CS) 2 - Featuring socio-technical cyber security warning systems</i> The paper introduces a socio-technical framework for cyber security warning systems, addressing the global need for coordinated efforts. Emphasizing the socio-technical nature of information systems security, it advocates for a platform, ST(CS)2, to bridge the gap between warning disseminators and recipients. The framework proposes a distinction between general and guided warnings, customizing threat levels and countermeasures.	Industrial operations – Telecommunication
(Ahmed et al., 2016)	<i>A SCADA system testbed for cybersecurity and forensic research and pedagogy</i> The testbed, recently constructed at the University of New Orleans, distinguishes itself by utilizing standard industrial equipment, deviating from the more common and cost-effective practices of software simulations and virtualized environments.	Industrial operations – Water plant

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
(Yao et al., 2014)	<p>This physical representation ensures a more authentic and comprehensive understanding of SCADA systems compared to purely virtual alternatives.</p> <p><i>Integrated framework of wisdom manufacturing systems from semiotic perspective</i></p> <p>The paper addresses the modeling challenge of Wisdom Manufacturing (WM) systems by employing the onion and ladder models. These models, incorporating social, cyber, and physical systems, are analyzed using semiotics. The ladder model offers a comprehensive theoretical framework, rooted in semiotics, for the modeling and integration of manufacturing systems, shedding light on their diverse levels and paving the way for systematic analysis.</p>	Industrial operations – Manufacturing process
(Norman & Koehler, 2017)	<p><i>Cyber defense as a complex adaptive system: A model-based approach to strategic policy design</i></p> <p>This paper emphasizes the understudied aspect of effective cybersecurity policy design in the context of increasing systems interdependence. The paper suggests that a rigorous, evidence-based approach is essential to grasp emergent organizational needs resulting from new cyber capabilities. The study highlights the complexity and unpredictability of the impacts of cybersecurity policies and emphasizes the need for a systematic approach.</p>	Industrial operations
(Egor, 2020)	<p><i>Digital Transformation of Industrial Companies: What is Management 4.0?</i></p> <p>The article explores the Industry 4.0 or the 4th Industrial Revolution, emphasizing the need to shift focus from technical aspects to managerial aspects in the context of digitalization within manufacturing companies. It highlights that digitalization involves integrating processes, including production, logistics, and personnel, with a strong connection between the physical and virtual environments through information and communication technologies. The evolving technologies in digital transformation are crucial for ensuring a company's success and future readiness.</p>	Industrial operations
(Hofbauer et al., 2019)	<p><i>Autonomous CPS mobility securely designed</i></p> <p>This position paper discusses the development of a system to support the design of a digital interlocking system for autonomous trains on less-used secondary railway lines, termed "Railway Operation as a Service." The focus is on creating a meta-model that considers safety, security, interoperability, and socio-technical aspects for the holistic modeling of the system at design time. The paper outlines the motivation, challenges, and potential benefits of this research, emphasizing the need for less expensive systems tailored to secondary lines.</p>	Railway
(Ouchani, 2021)	<p><i>A security policy hardening framework for Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems</i></p> <p>This paper addresses the challenges associated with ensuring safety, correctness, and security in Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems (SCPS), which encompass diverse aspects such as physical, technical, cybernetic, and social components. The focus is on formal methods to precisely model SCPS entities, their behavior, and interactions, as well as to specify and analyze security requirements and policies. The proposed approach is validated on a real SCPS scenario involving social</p>	Others

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	and technical threats, demonstrating its effectiveness and efficiency.	
(Nguyen, 2019)	<i>Formal requirements and constraints modelling in FORM-L for the engineering of complex socio-technical systems</i> Socio-technical systems integrate human behavior, physical processes, and computing, often termed "cyber-physical systems" or "systems of systems." These complex systems require collaboration across various disciplines and stakeholders throughout their lifetimes. EDF has developed the Formal Requirements Modelling Language (FORM-L) to address dynamic phenomena in system engineering. FORM-L supports a range of activities, including scoping studies, requirements elicitation, design, optimization, and testing. While the language and methodology are well-defined, tool development is ongoing to enhance support for these activities.	Industrial operations
(Pessoa et al., 2022)	<i>Model-Based Digital Threads for Socio-Technical Systems</i> This paper explores the application of Model-Based System Engineering (MBSE) in designing a digital thread for a Traffic Monitoring System (TMS) in a smart city. The study provides insights into digital twin development methodologies, leveraging Systems Modeling Languages (SysML's) high-level system engineering support, and demonstrates its applicability through a smart TMS case study. Future work includes SysML v2 utilization and full digital twin development.	Road
(Kaberuka & Johnson, 2020)	<i>Adapting STPA-sec for Socio-technical Cyber Security Challenges in Emerging Nations: A Case Study in Risk Management for Rwandan Health Care</i> This paper addresses socio-technical cybersecurity challenges in healthcare in emerging nations, focusing on a Rwandan hospital's Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS). The study employs the STPA-sec framework, integrating NIST controls. Ethnographic techniques and interviews support the adaptation of STPA-sec, considering socio-technical contexts. The study encourages further research on cybersecurity workforce development, budget constraints, and the holistic approach's adaptability to other emerging nations.	Healthcare
(Kacianka & Pretschner, 2021)	<i>Designing accountable systems</i> This paper introduces a method using Structural Causal Models (SCMs) to express and compare different definitions of accountability. SCMs, known for formalizing causality, offer a unique suitability for capturing the varied aspects of accountability. The paper emphasizes the importance of understanding causal mechanisms for any notion of accountability, making SCMs a powerful tool for system analysis and improvement.	Automotive
(Hariharan et al., 2023)	<i>Customers' Perception of Cybersecurity Risks in E-Commerce Websites</i> This study explores the impact of a cyber-attack on customers' perceptions in the context of an e-commerce platform by aligning STRIDE threat modeling with the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) cybersecurity requirements. Findings indicate that confidentiality compromise has the highest negative impact, with 82% of respondents expressing perceived privacy risks due to a cyber-attack. The study	IT

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	emphasizes the importance of robust cybersecurity measures, transparent communication, customer education, and prompt response during cyber-attacks to build and maintain trust in the evolving digital economy.	
(Neal et al., 2021)	<i>The potential of industry 4.0 Cyber Physical System to improve quality assurance: An automotive case study for wash monitoring of returnable transit items</i> The paper discusses the use of a Cyber-Physical System (CPS) in the automotive industry to improve quality by monitoring Returnable Transit Items (RTIs). The system uses passive RFID tags for identification and a network of RFID portals integrated within the RTI environment. This research highlights the potential of CPS in enhancing real-time monitoring and control of manufacturing processes in the context of Industry 4.0.	Automotive
(Viganò, 2022)	<i>Formal Methods for Socio-technical Security: (Formal and Automated Analysis of Security Ceremonies)</i> The paper emphasizes the necessity to include humans in the “security loop” and the importance of taking a socio-technical systems perspective when dealing with cyber security problems. Authors identify in formal methods the key to reach such goal.	IT
(Moraitis et al., 2023)	<i>Exploring the Cyber-Physical Threat Landscape of Water Systems: A Socio-Technical Modelling Approach</i> Authors propose a risk assessment framework for water utilities which takes into account socio-technical aspects. The framework includes: the estimation of the vulnerability probabilities and attack characteristics, the formulation of a representative set of scenarios, the run of cyber-physical stress-testing, and the final calculation of the system risk.	Industrial operations – water sector
(Simone et al., 2023)	<i>Thinking in Systems, Sifting Through Simulations: A Way Ahead for Cyber Resilience Assessment</i> This paper presents a novel systemic method which upgrades STPA-Sec, namely, STPA-Sec/S. This latter is grounded on the principles of STAMP and STPA but suggests the completion of the analysis of cyber-related failures including simulation-based resilience assessment. The method is evaluated in a water treatment plant setting.	Industrial operations – water sector
(Stojkovski & Lenzini, 2021)	<i>A workflow and toolchain proposal for analyzing users' perceptions in cyber threat intelligence sharing platforms</i> In this paper authors address the problem of risk perception among human users as part of a cyber socio technical system. As such, the paper discusses the benefits of a socio-technical approach to foster secure education and training support.	IT
(Tonkin et al., 2022 C.E.)	<i>Simulating cyber security management: A gamified approach to executive decision making</i> IN this paper authors present Aurelius, a simulation game about cyber security. The game is designed for managers to train them about the correlation between cyber security policies and business outcomes.	Finance
(Radanliev et al., 2020)	<i>Artificial intelligence and machine learning in dynamic cyber risk analytics at the edge</i> The paper discuss how artificial intelligence can be integrated in cyber risk analytics. As such, a framework is presented by authors. The framework rely on a taxonomy which details the	IT

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	requirements for predictive cyber risk analytics in environment in which AI components are present.	
(Patriarca, Simone, et al., 2022)	<i>Modelling cyber resilience in a water treatment and distribution system</i> In this paper authors present a cyber resilience assessment methodology based on simulations. The methodology spans from system design to the definition of specific performance indicators to evaluate cyber resilience. A case study related to a water treatment plant connected to a water distribution network is presented.	Industrial operations – water sector
(Kacianka et al., 2019)	<i>Extending causal models from machines into humans</i> In this paper, authors discuss the difficulties and the importance in utilizing causal model to map human behaviors within a socio-technical system. Authors state that a socio-technical perspective is necessary to deal with cyber physical systems which are well integrated in societal contexts.	Automotive
(Sudeikat & Köhler-Bußmeier, 2022)	<i>On Combining Domain Modeling and Organizational Modeling for Developing Adaptive Cyber-Physical Systems</i> Authors integrate the SGAM architecture model providing an optional extension which prepares agent-oriented practices. Such integration enables: static analysis of the system, a simulation based analysis of the system, the use of the organization model as a system element itself to be optimized for adaptation.	Others
(Roy & Dey, 2023)	<i>Route Choice-Based Socio-Technical Macroscopic Traffic Model</i> The paper presents a novel model for traffic evaluation which integrates the human choices thus adopting a socio-technical perspective.	Road
(Nicho & Girija, 2022)	<i>Systems Dynamics Modeling for Evaluating Socio-Technical Vulnerabilities in Advanced Persistent Threats</i> This paper applies system dynamics simulations modelling to visualize the interactions between system variables in light of a successful cyber attack targeting the organization. Authors point out that the proposed methodology can be useful for evaluating wat-if cyber attack scenarios.	Industrial operations
(Cimini et al., 2020)	<i>A human-in-the-loop manufacturing control architecture for the next generation of production systems</i> This paper proposes a novel framework to integrate humans into manufacturing environments and smart factories. To this purpose, authors review existing taxonomies and framework for human / machine integration.	Industrial operations
(Perrotin et al., 2022)	<i>HoS-ML: Socio-Technical System ADL Dedicated to Human Vulnerability Identification</i> Authors state that human factors play a vital role in cyber security. As such, they propose a human-oriented description language that permits – when integrated with Bayesian networks – to simulate humans vulnerabilities and estimate the impact of cyber attacks.	Industrial operations
(Suk et al., 2021)	<i>A Framework for Improving Rural Microgrid Sustainability Through Integrated Socio-technical Considerations</i> The paper present a method which relies on compromise decision support problem to support decision making for microgrid in rural environment. The problem balances the life	Industrial operations – electrical grid

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	quality of citizens with the sustainability of the power management.	

3.4.3. Manuscripts related with the information flow modelling

This section describes and summarizes the most relevant papers related to control theory modelling techniques, as reported in Table 7.

Table 7 – . Summary table of the most relevant paper related to information flow modelling

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
(Cadzow, 2019)	<i>The Analysis of the Socio-Technical Environment (STE) of Online Sextortion Using Case Studies and Published Reports from a Cybersecurity Perspective</i> This paper delves into the Socio-Technical Environment (STE) of online Sextortion in the Digital Society. The paper recommends a holistic planning approach, the development of a cyber deterrence strategy by law enforcement, enhanced recording and auditing of digital evidence, expanded use of IP blocking, increased collaboration between stakeholders for cybersecurity education, and the development of software and AI tools by technology companies to proactively identify false profiles.	IT
(Charitoudi & Blyth, 2014)	<i>An agent-based socio-technical approach to impact assessment for cyber defense</i> This paper introduces a novel simulation method for estimating the impact of cyber attacks, addressing limitations in existing approaches that often focus on individual levels such as assets or business processes. The proposed interdependency impact assessment approach emphasizes the dynamic relationships and dependencies within a supply chain, employing an agent-based socio-technical model. The model aims to enhance situational awareness for cyber defense, particularly focusing on critical information infrastructures.	Industrial operations – Supply chain
(Islam et al., 2019)	<i>A Socio-Technical and Co-evolutionary Framework for Reducing Human-Related Risks in Cyber Security and Cybercrime Ecosystems</i> This paper addresses the limited focus on the human element in cybersecurity, emphasizing the need for a broader framework that incorporates theoretical concepts and technological solutions to mitigate human-related risks. The investigation identifies the gap in existing research and introduce a socio-technical framework designed to comprehensively understand human-related risks within cyber security and cybercrime ecosystems. The framework considers various human actors, including offenders, preventers, promoters, responders, and victims.	Road
(Gronau, 2021)	<i>Modeling the Handling of Knowledge for Industry 4.0</i> The paper addresses the need for an analysis and design method for knowledge management that integrates human and machine interactions in the Industry 4.0 era. It introduces KMDL3.0, an extended modeling language, as a tool to represent, analyze,	Industrial operations

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	and optimize knowledge processing with a focus on artificial intelligence and machine learning in both office and production environments.	
(Mertzani et al., 2023)	<i>Expertise, social influence, and knowledge aggregation in distributed information processing</i> The article explores knowledge aggregation in socio-technical systems using Nowak's Regulatory Theory of Social Influence (RTSI). It introduces an algorithm, implemented in SMARTSIS, a multi-agent simulator, showcasing its effectiveness in self-organizing Distributed Information Processing (DIP) units. This interdisciplinary work bridges multi-agent systems and social psychology, offering a computational representation of human psychology for enhanced knowledge management in diverse systems, providing a foundation for effective self-awareness and reflection within distributed information processing units.	Others
(Kianpour et al., 2020)	<i>From Cyber Incidents to Training Cognitive Situation Management: *Work in Progress</i> This paper presents early results of a wider research dealing with cyber security situation modelling. The researcher leverages on cyber ranges to train cognitive evaluation of cyber risk.	Others
(El-Haouzi et al., 2021)	<i>Social dimensions in cps & iot based automated production systems</i> The paper investigates three models of sociability as a way to integrate humans in automated production systems: the first model deals with the classical human-system interaction interfaces and embedded sensing systems; the second model aims to take advantage from existing social network services, the last model relates to the design of an industrial system as a society, linking smart connected objects through a typology of social relations.	Industrial operations – production systems
(Kowalski & Østby, 2022)	<i>A Socio-Technical Regime Transitions Model for Gerontechnology Service Design: Privacy, Information Security and Cyber Security in Focus</i> The paper investigates aging in place of healthcare system with respect to cyber vulnerabilities. Authors leverage on cyber range to perform their study. The study is incomplete and only partial results are presented.	Healthcare
(Andreassen et al., 2023)	<i>InCREASE: A Dynamic Framework Towards Enhancing Situational Awareness in Cyber Incident Response</i> In this paper, authors introduce InCREASE, a dynamic framework for enhancing situation awareness in cyber incident response. The framework models communication behavior and information flows between cybersecurity stakeholders to coordinate the management of cybersecurity operations.	IT
(Lindhout & Reniers, 2022)	<i>The “Transparency for Safety” Triangle: Developing a Smart Transparency Framework to Achieve a Safety Learning Community</i> Authors study the importance of transparency of information to respond to disruption in cyber-socio-technical systems. Accordingly, authors develop a transparency standard framework to map information flows. The framework extends the holistic TEAM safety culture model.	Industrial operations

3.4.4. Review on system theory modelling approach

This study undertakes a thorough examination, focusing on the research convergence on CSTSs and their modeling methodologies. The previous analysis reveals a notable large quantity of documents utilizing control theory modeling to investigate CSTSs. Consequently, this section refines the systemic literature review to precisely delineate the research objectives and investigate the diverse techniques and methodologies employed in mapping and analyzing these complex systems.

Therefore, this section's emphasis is placed on system theory and its associated techniques, identified as the most widely accepted and investigated approach for CSTS modeling over the last years. Hence, the research employs a structured query strategy within the Scopus database, focusing on relevant literature published between 2020 and 2024, aligning with the publication of a seminal review on the System theory approach in 2020 (Patriarca, Chatzimichailidou, et al., 2022). The query structure is outlined as follows following Scopus semantics:

“TITLE-ABS-KEY ("cyber" AND ("system theor* accident model* process*" OR "system* theor* accident model* and process*" OR "system* theor* process analysis" OR "system* theor* process and analysis" OR ("causal analysis" AND "system* theor*")) OR "STAMP analysis") AND PUBYEAR > 2020 AND PUBYEAR < 2025”*

The query design has been tailored to retrieve papers specifically addressing cyber-related topics and employing various system-theoretic frameworks, such as STAMP analysis and its associated techniques such as STPA and CAST. Then following the same methodology and criteria used in the previous section, the study extracted 24 documents. Additionally, papers not considered in the analysis have been excluded for various reasons. Among them, four of them related to computing modeling (4), one focused on organizational modeling (1), one was a summary of conference proceedings (1), and another was a book chapter (1), one refer to vacuum robotic applications (1), two solely addressed technical aspects without considering cyber-socio elements (2), and two were solely focused on cyber aspects without relevance to socio-technical considerations (2) and other two articles that are not fully available in the database (2). This process let the 10 articles that have been considered relevant for further analysis, after screening. These relevant articles cover various domains of application, including Industrial operations (4), Automotive (3), Maritime (2), and IT (1), as briefly summarized above. In addition, Table 8 provides a brief description of each paper.

Table 8 – . Summary table of the most relevant paper related to system theory

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
(Simone et al., 2023)	<i>Thinking in Systems, Sifting Through Simulations: A Way Ahead for Cyber Resilience Assessment</i> See Table 6.	Industrial operations – Water plant processes
(Zacharaki et al., 2021)	<i>Decision making with STPA through markov decision process, a theoretic framework for safe human-robot collaboration</i> The research develops a methodology using POMDP associating the STPA to merge nominal and unsafe actions in collaborative robots, addressing safety challenges in human-	Industrial operations – Human–Robot collaborative manufacturing task

<i>Citation</i>	<i>Title and summary of the paper</i>	<i>Domain of application</i>
	assisted manufacturing. Evaluated in a simulated human-robot scenario, the methodology identifies both loss and hazard scenarios, offering a proactive safety approach.	
(Ghosh et al., 2023)	<i>An Integrated Approach of Threat Analysis for Autonomous Vehicles Perception System</i> The authors want to propose a robust threat analysis and risk assessment framework with mathematical modeling to identify cyber-physical threats to Automated Vehicles (AVs) perception systems that are critical for the driving behaviors and complex interaction of AVs in their operational design domain. A comparative threat analysis for an AV perception system with the ISO/SAE 21434 standard and a STPA-Sec approach is demonstrated.	Automotive
(Sahay et al., 2023)	<i>A comparative risk analysis on CyberShip system with STPA-Sec, STRIDE and CORAS</i> The authors evaluate and compare the application of three risk assessment methodologies for identifying threats and vulnerabilities in a CyberShip System. STPA-Sec, STRIDE and CORAS are the proposed methodologies.	Maritime
(Carreras Guzman et al., 2021)	<i>A Comparative Study of STPA-Extension and the UfOI-E Method for Safety and Security Co-analysis</i> In this paper the authors bridge the gap between two novel safety and security co-analysis methods and their practical implementation. At the end a tailored combination of STPA-Extension and UfOI-E is proposed.	Maritime
(Lee & Madnick, 2021)	<i>Cybersafety Approach to Cybersecurity Analysis and Mitigation for Mobility-as-a Service and Internet of Vehicles</i> Since traditional hazard analysis methods are limited in their ability to account for interactions among organizational, sociotechnical, human and technical components, in this paper the cybersafety method, based on STPA and STPA-Sec was developed to meet the growing need to holistically analyze complex sociotechnical systems.	Automotive
(Kaneko et al., 2019)	<i>Threat analysis using STRIDE with STAMP/STPA</i> In this paper a method of threat analysis using STRIDE with the STAMP and STPA procedures is proposed.	IT
(Gautham et al., 2022)	<i>STPA-driven Multilevel Runtime Monitoring for In-time Hazard Detection</i> In this paper the authors developed a workflow model that connects STPA hazard causation information to lower-level runtime monitoring to detect hazards at the operational phase. The authors demonstrated and evaluated the value of multilevel monitors by injecting hazards on an autonomous emergency braking system model.	Others
(Liew et al., 2021)	<i>A Novel System-Theoretic Matrix-Based Approach to Analysing Safety and Security of Cyber-Physical Systems</i> In this paper, the authors present a novel methodology that leverages not only STPA, but also custom matrices to ensure a more comprehensive S&S.	Industrial operations – Energy storage
(Khan & Madnick, 2021)	<i>Cybersafety: A System-Theoretic Approach to Identify Cyber-Vulnerabilities and Mitigation Requirements in Industrial Control Systems</i> STAMP offers a powerful framework to analyze complex systems; hitherto, cybersecurity analysis of Industrial Control Systems (ICS) with stamp has not been published; thus, this	Industrial operations

Citation	Title and summary of the paper	Domain of application
	paper demonstrated the application of a STAMP based method, called Cybersafety, to identify and mitigate cyber vulnerabilities in ICS.	

In addition to the summary in Table 8 of the most relevant papers, the report provides details of each paper to highlight and explain the overall research purpose, the methodology employed to achieve the objectives, and briefly state the results obtained in the study.

Thinking in Systems, Sifting Through Simulations: A Way Ahead for Cyber Resilience Assessment

The manuscript discusses the evolving challenges of the CPSs within socio-technical systems. It highlights the vulnerability of these systems to cyber-related disruptions and the flaw of traditional risk analysis in addressing such complex issues. Therefore, the research introduces System-Theoretic Process Analysis for Security (STPA-Sec) as an associated technique of the STAMP model, aiming to identify and address cyber threats in socio-technical systems, to further presents System-Theoretic Process Analysis for Security with Simulations (STPA-Sec/S), a methodological interface that combines STPA-Sec with quantitative resilience assessment through simulation models. The case study on a water treatment plant demonstrates the feasibility of this approach, providing insights for decision-makers in enhancing cyber resilience across various industries. Therefore, the research underscores the need for novel methodologies to address the cyber vulnerabilities of critical system’s component. Therefore, the paper defines the STPA-Sec/S as a solution to assess cyber resilience, emphasizing its applicability beyond the water supply sector and its potential impact on decision-making processes throughout the lifecycle of a system.

Decision making with STPA through markov decision process, a theoretic framework for safe human-robot collaboration

The investigation examines the widespread use of collaborative robots in industry to assist humans in manufacturing tasks. While these robots are designed to be safe, the integration of external sensors and cyber-physical systems for close cooperation with humans can introduce new safety risks and hazards. Therefore, the authors propose a method that utilizes partially observable Markov decision processes (POMDP) to combine nominal system actions with Unsafe Control Actions (UCAs) identified through STPA. The work contributes to creating a decision-making tool based on STPA hazard analysis and Markov decision processes. This tool serves as a hazard assessment monitoring tool during the operational phase, actively triggering the system to choose actions that enhance safety. The integration of STPA outcomes into a POMDP model offsets for uncertainties arising from sensor measurements and human behavior errors.

An Integrated Approach of Threat Analysis for Autonomous Vehicles Perception System

Automated Vehicles are a revolutionary step in mobility and these are equipped with sophisticated perception sensors, high-performance computer, AI-driven algorithms, and connectivity with other IoT; this has the consequences that AVs can be considered as a special kind of CPS and the scope of this work is to address this problem in order to have a robust threat modeling framework for AV applications. In this work a comparative threat analysis for an AV perception system with the ISO/SAE 21434 standard and a STPA-Sec approach is demonstrated in this paper, proposing then a robust threat analysis and risk assessment framework with mathematical modeling to identify cyber-

physical threats to AV perception systems that are critical for the driving behaviors and complex interaction of AVs in their operational design domain.

A comparative risk analysis on CyberShip system with STPA-Sec, STRIDE and CORAS

The widespread use of software-intensive cyber systems in structures as ships opened new avenues for cyber-attacks to potentially disrupt operations. In this work the authors proposed methodologies to assess cyber risks to identify cyber threats and vulnerabilities that can be exploited to compromise cyber systems. In this paper three risk assessment methodologies have been applied: STPA-Sec, STRIDE and CORAS; the result found is that the STPA-Sec is good at identifying hazards by looking at the control actions and the structure of CyberShip system.

A Comparative Study of STPA-Extension and the UFoI-E Method for Safety and Security Co-analysis

Emerging challenges in CPSs have been encouraging the development of safety and security co-analysis methods. This paper aims to fill the gap between two novel safety and security co-analysis methods and their practical implementations; specifically, here a novel extension of the System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA-Extension) and the Uncontrolled Flows of Information Energy (UFoI-E) method are compared through a common case study: the CPS under analysis is a conceptual autonomous ship. The two methods are analyzed independently of each other and, at the end, a tailored combination of these methods is proposed.

Cybersafety Approach to Cybersecurity Analysis and Mitigation for Mobility-as-a Service and Internet of Vehicles

Urban mobility is in the midst of a revolution and technological advancements often lead to new hazards and, coupled with the increased level of automation and connectivity in the new generation of autonomous vehicles, cybersecurity is emerging as a key threat affecting these vehicles. Since traditional hazard analysis methods are limited in their ability to account for interactions among organizational, sociotechnical, human and technical components, in this paper the cybersafety method, based on System Theoretic processes (STPA and STPA-Sec) was developed to meet the growing need to holistically analyze complex sociotechnical systems. The results are then compared with another promising method known as Combined Harm Analysis of Safety and Security for Information Systems (CHASSIS) and both methods were applied to the Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) and Internet of Vehicles (IoV) use cases. In particular, cybersafety demonstrated the ability to identify hazards due to unsafe/unsecure interactions among sociotechnical components.

Threat analysis using STRIDE with STAMP/STPA

In this paper a method of threat analysis using STRIDE with the STAMP and STPA procedures is proposed. STPA and STPA-Sec procedures are better than STPA-SafeSec steps for extracting safety and security risks in early stages of development. The result is that, according to the authors, it is better to incorporate the STRIDE threat analysis into the STPA-Sec procedure. Specifically, the STRIDE model is applied to the smart grid case discussed in a previous SafeSec paper.

STPA-driven Multilevel Runtime Monitoring for In-time Hazard Detection

The authors developed an integrative approach to in-time hazard detection that incorporates system-level analysis into the design of runtime monitoring architectures. Integrative approaches to runtime monitoring for hazard detection in CPS are needed to augment the technical basis for DepDevOps

style methods. They demonstrated that the systematic nature of System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) hazard analysis is beneficial in deriving and refining multilevel monitoring properties related to causal factors. By developing monitors across multiple system levels, we can accurately detect the origin of a hazard even when it propagates errors across different CPS levels. In other words, when faults go undetected at their original location, monitors at other system levels can detect propagated errors, thus increasing hazard detection coverage. The authors also found that MBDE methods and tools significantly improve the productivity of STPA and assist in evaluating runtime monitoring schemes for hazard coverage and refinement.

A Novel System-Theoretic Matrix-Based Approach to Analysing Safety and Security of Cyber-Physical Systems

In this paper, the authors review a selection of existing works which adopt or extend STPA for addressing both Safety and Security of CPS and, in particular, two major gaps: (a) little or no explicit guidance on deriving Security requirements; and (b) lack of discussion on overseeing the correlations between the derived Safety and Security requirements. In particular here a novel methodology leverages not only STPA, but also custom matrices to ensure a more comprehensive Safety and Security (S&S) analysis and the proposed methodology is demonstrated using a case study of particular commercial cloud-based monitoring and control system for residential energy storage systems.

Cybersafety: A System-Theoretic Approach to Identify Cyber-Vulnerabilities and Mitigation Requirements in Industrial Control Systems

Recent cyber-physical attacks have invoked an ominous realization about the vulnerability of critical infrastructure; thus, there is an urgent need to analyze the safety and security of critical infrastructure in a holistic fashion, leveraging the physics of the cyber-physical system. This work uses the electrical generation and distribution system of an archetypal industrial facility to demonstrate the application of a System Theoretic Accident Model (STAMP) based method, called Cybersafety, to identify and mitigate cyber-vulnerabilities in Industrial Control Systems (ICS). The key contribution of this work is to differentiate the additional steps required to perform a holistic cybersecurity analysis for an ICS of significant size and complexity and to present the analysis in a structured format that can be emulated for larger systems

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the exploration of CSTSs in complex and dynamic scenarios has been illustrated giving critical insights into the evolving landscape of industrial operations and joint safety/security management challenges. The emergence of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 paradigms has driven the integration of advanced technologies, such as the IoT and AI, into industrial processes, thereby enhancing efficiency and functionality. However, this integration in systems delivers novel complexities. The notion of CSTSs is here used to underscore the intricate interplay among cyber-technical artifacts, human operators, and organizational structures, that pave the way to higher system complexity and non-linear potential disruption scenarios. While traditional safety and risk management approaches have historically focused on prevention and protection strategies, the evolving nature of modern industrial systems demands a change in thinking towards resilience modeling, control theory

modeling, and information flow modeling. These approaches offer the capacity to adapt to and recover from unforeseen events, ensuring the continued operation and security of industrial systems.

It is worth mentioning that this literature review has laid the foundation for further research and exploration in the field of CSTSs modeling, providing a comprehensive overview of the current state of knowledge and highlighting areas for future investigation. This report serves as a resource for advancing the understanding of CSTSs modelling in industrial settings and informing strategies for securing the future of industrial systems in an increasingly interconnected and dynamic environment.

Hence, the results of the study showed that journal articles focus more on complex systems but report the analytical steps and results less completely. By contrast, conference papers tend to deal with simpler systems and usually include most of the analysis steps and respective findings. Relying on this observation, control theory modelling is the most used modelling approach. It is deduced that this condition verifies being control theory able to clearly map the interactions between humans and technical artifacts both physical and especially the cyber ones, bringing them closer to traditional automation control, and somehow, transferable to human-machine or human-human control loops. Among control theory modelling, system-theoretic approaches turned out to be effective for dealing with complex CSTSs. As such, this report concludes that system theory can represent the foundational basis for future developments of systems that aim to be more resilient to cyber threats, as for the scope of the RESIST project.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) – Mission 4 Education and Research – Component 2 From research to business - Investment 1.1, Prin 2022 Notice announced with DD No. 104 of 2/2/2022, entitled RESIST - RESilience management to Industrial Systems Threats, proposal code 2022YSAE2X

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ANNEX A – Resilience engineering modelling papers details

In addition to the summary table of the most relevant paper adopting the resilience engineering modelling approach. Annex A describes more details of each paper in which highlight and explain the overall research, the methodology to achieve the objectives and briefly the results obtained with a quick conclusion.

'Black Swans', 'Dragon Kings' and Beyond: Towards Predictability and Suppression of Extreme All-Hazards Events Through Modeling and Simulation

The paper discusses the challenges posed by undesired events, both NATECH and human-made, on regional, national, and global systems. It emphasizes the need for understanding and predicting these events to enhance resilience and minimize their impacts. The examples of disasters such as Hurricane Katrina, Hurricane Sandy, Alberta Floods, and Super Typhoon Haiyan underscore the vulnerability of communities to unexpected shocks. The term “Black Swans” is used to represent unpredictable events that fall outside regular expectations and have a profound impact on various systems. Unlike Black Swans, Dragon Kings may possess properties that make them not only identifiable in real-time but also predictable. The evolving science on complexity, particularly complex networks and resilience, suggests that modeling and simulation can aid in predicting and suppressing low-probability, high-consequence events. This includes natural hazards like floods, earthquakes, wildfires, tsunamis, extreme weather, as well as cyber-attacks and financial events. The utilization of recent advances in complex network theory is proposed to enhance the resiliency of critical physical and digital infrastructure owned by governments and other stakeholders.

Towards a generic resilience management, quantification and development process: General definitions, requirements, methods, techniques and measures, and case studies

The paper tackles the limitations of existing risk management standards, such as ISO 31000 and IEC 61508, by proposing an advanced resilience framework. Going beyond traditional risk approaches, it introduces a comprehensive resilience management process that covers resilience levels, general requirements, and a taxonomy of methods. The framework focuses on addressing unexpected, disruptive events, emphasizing the importance of technical system resilience and organizational capabilities. Noteworthy aspects include the incorporation of cyber-physical socio-technical systems, diverse security dimensions, and a method ontology consisting of 30 categories. The paper employs three case studies, including a disruption effect simulation for the Swiss energy grid, to exemplify the application of the proposed framework. Emphasizing a science-driven approach, the work aims to establish standards for resilience management applicable across diverse disciplines, including STEM, social sciences, psychology, ecology, economics, ethics, and political sciences. The presented resilience framework aspires to facilitate credible certification for critical infrastructure and safety-critical systems by providing a comprehensive and tailorable approach to resilience management, quantification, development, and implementation.

WAX: An integrated conceptual framework for the analysis of cyber-socio-technical systems

This paper delves into knowledge creation and conversion within cyber-socio-technical systems (CSTSs), emphasizing the intertwined relationships in modern work domains. It introduces the Work-As-x (WAX) framework, exploring different work representations generated by various agents. The framework's fractal and recursive nature allows adaptable granularity levels for analyzing work practices in diverse socio-technical systems, aligning with challenges posed by digitalization and

Industry 4.0. While applicable to safety management, its scope extends to security and performance management systems, highlighting the importance of systemic research and abandoning reductionist approaches for a deeper understanding of interactions and implications in evolving work environments. The WAX framework promotes organizational learning, emphasizing adaptation as a key to success in dynamic settings.

MARLIN Method: Enhancing Warehouse Resilience in Response to Disruptions

The study delves into the operational dynamics of supply chains, focusing on their impact on wholesale warehouses and their resilience in the face of disruptive events, particularly exemplified by the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. It introduces the MARLIN (Method wAREhouse ResiLience dIstruptionN) method, grounded in resilience engineering theories, as a practical tool for identifying and responding to key intervention areas during disruptions. An empirical test conducted in an Italian warehouse substantiates the efficacy of the MARLIN method, revealing tangible results and underscoring its value for disruption management. This method, conceived to address disruptions in warehouse management, fills a gap in existing research that has concentrated on handling disruptions in supplier or final echelons of the supply chain. It highlights the pivotal role of logistics and warehouse management in the broader context of complex cyber-socio-technical systems. The study elucidates the application of the MARLIN method through a detailed case study, demonstrating its effectiveness in recognizing areas requiring intervention and identifying KPIs related to disruptions. The iterative and cyclical nature of the methodology allows for the identification of impact patterns and effective intervention strategies. Furthermore, the study outlines the importance of defining environmental areas in the context of disruptions, enabling objective and measurable analysis. The study contributes to the resilience engineering literature, providing a valuable methodology for enhancing warehouse resilience and adaptive capabilities in the face of disruptions.

Security and resilience for airport infrastructure

This paper focuses on the security situation of airports in Europe, particularly addressing the vulnerability to combined cyber-physical threats. It discusses the ongoing EU-H2020 project SATIE (Security of Air Transport Infrastructure of Europe) and its approach to enhancing the security of airports through a security toolkit. The toolkit employs a multi-faceted approach, augmenting the separation and security of the physical, control, and supervisory layers of airport security architecture. It utilizes video-captured biometric credentials and anomaly detection algorithms, feeding information into a model that quantitatively represents the propagation of negative impacts through the airport infrastructure. The paper emphasizes the impact assessment simulation within the SATIE toolkit, utilizing Agent-Based Modeling (ABM) to represent not only technical components but also the social aspect of airport systems. The current focus is on passenger movement and their interactions with technical components such as the Flight Information Display System (FIDS). The simulation tool aims to contribute to the SATIE project by providing insights into the impact of combined cyber-physical attacks on airport infrastructure. It allows for the analysis of individual passenger movement in both normal and disturbed operations, simulating scenarios such as a cyber-attack on the FIDS. The results demonstrate crowd formations and the impact of the attack on airport functionality. Additionally, the tool enables the quantitative analysis and comparison of the system's degradation for different recovery situations. The SATIE toolkit offers a comprehensive approach to airport security, improving correlations between physical and cyber threats, enhancing forensics investigations, and enabling dynamic impact assessments for effective threat prevention, detection, response, and mitigation.

Beyond Murphy's Law: Applying Wider Human Factors Behavioural Science Approaches in Cyber-Security Resilience: An Applied Practice Case Study Discussing Approaches to Assessing Human Factors Vulnerabilities in Cyber-Security Systems

The paper discusses novel approaches to cyber-security resilience, which relies on three pillars: people, process, and technology. The authors argue that in any complex socio-technical system, human behavior can disrupt the secure and efficient running of the system with risk accumulating through individual and system-wide errors and compromised security behaviors that may be exploited by actors with malicious intent. As such, authors pointed at Human Factor disciplines to be necessary to deal with the problem of cyber-security resilience. The study discusses methods for vulnerability identification and risk assessment, with a focus on modeling large, dynamic, and complex socio-technical systems. The study's major finding is that among those methods, the most effective are the ones considering cultural factors. This approach allows for a more comprehensive understanding of potential security risks within complex system.

Development and measurement of a resilience indicator for cyber-socio-technical systems: The allostatic load

The authors argue that in complex cyber-socio-technical systems, traditional resilience indicators may not fully capture the system's ability to adapt to stressors. They propose the concept of allostatic load, which is a measure of the cumulative wear and tear on the system due to repeated adaptation to stressors. The methodology used in the paper involves the use of semantic technologies, the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM), the WAX conceptual framework, and a crowd-based approach to elicit industrial knowledge. These tools are used to identify misalignments between formal organization documents or manager views (Work-As-Imagined), and actual work practices (Work-As-Done), which can lead to organizational tensions and safety incidents. The authors validate their approach with two real case studies related to: (i) a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant, and (ii) an enterprise in the aluminum sector. These case studies demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of the proposed methodology in measuring the allostatic load and, in turn, assessing the resilience of cyber-socio-technical systems.

CyberSecurity Readiness: A Model for SMEs based on the Socio-Technical Perspective

The paper addresses the cybersecurity readiness of small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The authors propose a CyberSecurity Readiness Model for SMEs (namely, CSRM-SME) based on a Socio-Technical view of the organization. This model was applied to three SMEs to evaluate its capability of assessing their cybersecurity readiness. The model enables a further understanding of the strategies adopted by the SMEs to prevent and manage cyber-attacks. The paper highlights that SMEs are among the most vulnerable and least mature in terms of cybersecurity resilience. As such, the authors argue that the rise in cybercrime presents significant challenges for SMEs, which have become reliant on digital technology for their day-to-day business operations. The CSRM-SME model provides a comprehensive framework for assessing cybersecurity readiness in SMEs, offering valuable insights into the strategies and environments that can help prevent and manage cyber-attacks.

Secure Safety; State-of-the-art and remaining challenges

The paper discusses the concept of SecureSafety (SeSa) in the context of Safety Instrumented Systems (SIS) in the oil and gas industry. The authors argue that the SeSa approach, which combines security and safety in the manufacturing of industrial control and automation systems, needs to be extended to counter unexpected events from security threats. They propose the resilience concept as

a foundation to complement SeSa approaches and measures. The paper explores the challenges of adopting key aspects of resilience to an increasingly software-intensive SIS domain and the potentially disruptive impact of innovative technologies such as 5G. The authors conclude by suggesting that the adaptation of the concept of resilience into the SeSa domain should be based on a sociotechnical perspective, to be contextualized into a procedural and compliance-oriented scheme. They also provide a roadmap for future work on SeSa resilience. In conclusion, the exploration of CSTSs within the CPSs in complex and dynamic scenarios has been illustrated giving critical insights into the evolving landscape of industrial operations and security challenges. The emergence of Industry 4.0 has driven the integration of advanced technologies, such as the IoT and AI, into industrial processes, thereby enhancing efficiency and functionality. However, this integration in systems delievers

ANNEX B – Control theory modelling papers details

In addition to the summary table of the most relevant paper adopting the control theory modelling approach. Annex B describes more details of each paper in which highlight and explain the overall research, the methodology to achieve the objectives and briefly the results obtained with a quick conclusion.

Using a socio-technical systems approach to design and support systems thinking in cyber security education

The investigation underscores the critical role of Information Security in safeguarding confidentiality, integrity, availability, authentication, and accountability of information via simulation systems. The researchers aim to bridge this gap by advocating for a STS approach, emphasizing systems thinking in the realm of cybersecurity education. The simulator aims to enhance students' understanding of adversarial and systems thinking. Therefore, the manuscript highlights the researchers' poster presentation, which outlines how the STS approach is employed to design and support an agent-based simulation tool. Three main attributes such as Resources, Skills, and Motivation have been identified as crucial factors influencing the behavior and performance of each actor within the simulation. The researchers plan to delve deeper into the Motivation attribute by conducting an extensive literature review on theories explaining attack actors' motivation and defense actors' motivation. This ongoing analysis aims to provide further evidence supporting the benefits of incorporating STS in cybersecurity education.

ST(CS) 2 - Featuring socio-technical cyber security warning systems. Summary and Highlights of Relevance:

The paper proposes a socio-technical framework for the development of cyber security warning systems. Then the research analyze existing global cyber security warning systems and identify a crucial gap related to the diverse perceptions of security risks and its countermeasures. Then it is possible to note that differing perceptions, laws, and policies hinder such development. To address this vulnerability, the investigation propose a platform called A Socio-Technical Cyber Security Coordination System (ST(CS)2). This platform aims to bridge the socio-technical gap between cyber security warning disseminators and end-recipients, improving the effectiveness of response measures. The distinction between general and guided cyber security warnings is highlighted, with guided warnings being customized based on the socio-technical security posture of the recipient. The paper emphasizes that this customization considers both social and technical factors, reflecting how security is understood and implemented. This approach aims to demonstrate the practical utility of the proposed framework in improving cyber security coordination and response.

A SCADA system testbed for cybersecurity and forensic research and pedagogy

The testbed, recently constructed at the University of New Orleans, distinguishes itself by utilizing standard industrial equipment, deviating from the more common and cost-effective practices of software simulations and virtualized environments. While this approach incurs higher expenses, it offers a substantial advantage in closely mirroring real-world SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) systems. The testbed is equipped with fully functional physical processes, a critical feature that enhances its suitability for both research endeavors and educational purposes. This physical representation ensures a more authentic and comprehensive understanding of SCADA systems compared to purely virtual alternatives.

Integrated framework of wisdom manufacturing systems from semiotic perspective

The paper addresses the modeling challenge of Wisdom Manufacturing (WM) systems by employing the onion and ladder models. These models, incorporating social, cyber, and physical systems, are analyzed using semiotics. The ladder model, applied to elucidate current integrated manufacturing systems, indicates that the disparity among existing systems hinges on the attained level of semiotics. In contrast, the WM system encompasses and integrates all semiotic levels. The ladder model offers a comprehensive theoretical framework, rooted in semiotics, for the modeling and integration of manufacturing systems, shedding light on their diverse levels and paving the way for systematic analysis.

Cyber defense as a complex adaptive system: A model-based approach to strategic policy design

The paper addresses the inadequate focus on effective cybersecurity policy design in the context of growing systems interdependence. It underscores the common implementation of cyber technologies without due consideration for human-technology interactions and the reciprocal impact of individual interactions on technology. The scenario discussed involves a government agency applying a complexity science perspective, incorporating agent-based modeling, to comprehend the ramifications of strategic policy decisions. A comprehensive, evidence-based approach is advocated for understanding the organizational needs accompanying new cyber capabilities. The study delves into a model that explores the socio-technical dynamics, offers insights gained from lessons, and urges further research and development. The discussion emphasizes the intricate and unpredictable nature of cybersecurity policy impacts, stressing the necessity for a systematic approach to address evolving challenges.

Digital Transformation of Industrial Companies: What is Management 4.0?

The article explores the Industry 4.0 or the 4th Industrial Revolution, emphasizing the need to shift focus from technical aspects to managerial aspects in the context of digitalization within manufacturing companies. It highlights that digitalization involves integrating processes, including production, logistics, and personnel, with a strong connection between the physical and virtual environments through information and communication technologies. The benefits include improved value chains, enhanced business models, and societal well-being. While Industry 4.0 technologies offer advantages like shorter production cycles and faster time-to-market, many companies still view digitalization as a formality. Successful digital transformation requires strong leadership, rational decisions, and competent staff. The evolving technologies in digital transformation are crucial for ensuring a company's success and future readiness.

Autonomous CPS mobility securely designed

This position paper delves into the development of a comprehensive system to facilitate the design of a digital interlocking system tailored for autonomous trains on less-utilized secondary railway lines, referred to as "Railway Operation as a Service." The primary focus is on constructing a meta-model that encompasses safety, security, interoperability (including 5G technology), and socio-technical aspects to holistically model the system during the design phase. The proposed meta-model incorporates a hierarchical structure and various perspectives, aiming to provide a thorough approach to the development of the interlocking system. The paper discusses the motivation behind this research, outlines associated challenges, and underscores the potential benefits, particularly the necessity for cost-effective systems tailored to secondary lines. Future steps involve the meticulous

definition of the use case, derivation and cataloging of components, identification of threats and vulnerabilities, and an assessment of the meta-model's applicability in a real-world scenario.

A security policy hardening framework for Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems

This paper delves into the intricate challenges posed by Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems (SCPS), encompassing heterogeneous subsystems with physical, technical, cybernetic, and social dimensions. The complexity arises in ensuring safety, correctness, and security, particularly against a spectrum of technical and socio-technical threats. To tackle this, the paper advocates for the use of formal methods to meticulously model SCPS entities, their behaviors, and interactions. Emphasis is placed on formalizing security policies and requirements. An algorithm is devised to automatically reinforce security policies and scrutinize the validity of requirements amidst potential attacks. Validation is conducted on a real SCPS scenario, affirming the efficacy and efficiency of the proposed framework. Future directions involve enhancing SCPS model expressiveness, reducing algorithmic complexity, integrating reinforcement learning, and expanding experiments to domains like smart manufacturing and automotive systems.

Formal requirements and constraints modelling in FORM-L for the engineering of complex socio-technical systems

Socio-technical systems integrate human behavior, physical processes, and computing, often termed "cyber-physical systems" or "systems of systems." These complex systems require collaboration across various disciplines and stakeholders throughout their lifetimes. EDF has developed the Formal Requirements Modelling Language (FORM-L) to address dynamic phenomena in system engineering. FORM-L supports a range of activities, including scoping studies, requirements elicitation, design, optimization, and testing. It emphasizes "thrifty modeling," enabling the composition of models for specific engineering tasks by assembling existing modules. While the language and methodology are well-defined, tool development is ongoing to enhance support for these activities.

Model-Based Digital Threads for Socio-Technical Systems

This chapter explores the application of Model-Based System Engineering (MBSE) in designing a digital thread for a Traffic Monitoring System (TMS) in a smart city. Emphasizing the use of Systems Modeling Language (SysML), it outlines how MBSE can establish traceability between requirements, design, analysis, and testing, fostering the development of digital twins. SysML v2 is discussed for its potential enhancements in supporting digital thread development for socio-technological systems. The study provides insights into digital twin development methodologies, leveraging SysML's high-level system engineering support, and demonstrates its applicability through a smart TMS case study. Future work includes SysML v2 utilization and full digital twin development.

Adapting STPA-sec for Socio-technical Cyber Security Challenges in Emerging Nations: A Case Study in Risk Management for Rwandan Health Care

This research focuses on the intricate cybersecurity challenges in healthcare within emerging nations, with a specific emphasis on a Rwandan hospital's Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS). The study introduces the STPA-sec framework, incorporating NIST controls. Given resource limitations, increasing demand, and evolving organizational structures, a holistic approach is proposed. Ethnographic techniques and iterative interviews are integral to adapting STPA-sec, especially in contexts with a shortage of trained analysts. Results underscore the necessity for additional methodological structure in regions with limited analysts and advocate for the framework's

application, backed by NIST controls. The study encourages further exploration of cybersecurity workforce development, budgetary constraints, and the broader adaptability of the holistic approach across diverse emerging nations.

Designing accountable systems

Accountability is a crucial aspect for various technical systems, including algorithmic decision systems, autonomous cyber-physical systems, and general software systems. However, the concept of accountability has a long and varied history, posing challenges for software developers to incorporate it into system design. This paper introduces a method using Structural Causal Models (SCMs) to express and compare different definitions of accountability. SCMs, known for formalizing causality, offer a unique suitability for capturing the varied aspects of accountability. Despite challenges in developing SCMs for socio-technical systems, they provide clarity for meaningful design decisions and help analyze systems to ensure accountability. The paper emphasizes the importance of understanding causal mechanisms for any notion of accountability, making SCMs a powerful tool for system analysis and improvement.

Customers' Perception of Cybersecurity Risks in E-Commerce Websites

This study explores the impact of a cyber-attack on customers' perceptions in the context of an e-commerce platform by aligning STRIDE threat modeling with the confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) cybersecurity requirements. Findings indicate that confidentiality compromise has the highest negative impact, with 82% of respondents expressing perceived privacy risks due to a cyber-attack. Notably, non-loyal customers are more concerned about purchasing securely, while loyal customers are emotionally affected to a greater extent. The study emphasizes the importance of robust cybersecurity measures, transparent communication, customer education, and prompt response during cyber-attacks to build and maintain trust in the evolving digital economy.

The potential of industry 4.0 Cyber Physical System to improve quality assurance: An automotive case study for wash monitoring of returnable transit items

The research focuses on the implementation of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) within the automotive industry. The study aims to improve quality and process compliance through the monitoring of Returnable Transit Items (RTIs). The paper discusses the socio-technical issues encountered during the real-world implementation of the system. The paper proposes the use of passive Ultra-High Frequency (UHF) Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags for the identification of metal RTIs. A distributed network of RFID portals was integrated within the RTI working environment. This research demonstrates the potential of CPS in enhancing real-time monitoring and control of manufacturing processes, contributing to the digital transformation of industrial value creation in the context of Industry 4.0.

Formal Methods for Socio-technical Security: (Formal and Automated Analysis of Security Ceremonies)

The paper argues the importance of considering human factors in cybersecurity as security is mainly a socio-technical problem, not just a technical one. The paper highlights that 95% of cyber-attacks are due to human error but, despite this, software engineers often neglect to take into account the human user as a component of the system's security. The author emphasizes the necessity to include humans in the "security loop" and the importance of taking a socio-technical systems perspective. As such the paper promotes the use of formal methods to establish the security of socio-technical systems, discussing some promising IT approaches.

Exploring the Cyber-Physical Threat Landscape of Water Systems: A Socio-Technical Modelling Approach

The paper studies the complex socio-technical dynamics and related uncertainties that govern the cyber-physical-threat landscape in water systems. The authors propose a socio-technical modelling approach to account for the adaptive balance between goal-driven behaviors and available skills of adversaries, exploitable vulnerabilities of assets, and the security posture of water utilities. This approach also includes an uncertainty-aware multi-scenario analysis to assess the risk level of water utilities against cyber-physical threats. The proposed risk assessment framework consists in a sequence of processes to: (i) estimate the vulnerability probabilities and attack characteristics, (ii) formulate a representative set of stochastically generated threat scenarios, (iii) conduct combined cyber-physical stress-testing of the system against the generated scenarios, and (iv) inferring the system's risk. The framework is tested by exploring different system's configurations of a hypothetical utility, showing how different cybersecurity practices and design traits affect the risk level.

Thinking in Systems, Sifting Through Simulations: A Way Ahead for Cyber Resilience Assessment

Discussed in Section 3.1.1.

A workflow and toolchain proposal for analyzing users' perceptions in cyber threat intelligence sharing platforms

The paper addresses the challenge of understanding users' perceptions of information sharing within the context of Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing platforms. The authors propose a conceptual workflow that verifies whether users have an accurate comprehension of how far information travels when shared in a CTI platform. The paper discusses the benefits of their socio-technical approach as a potential tool for security analysis, simulation, or education/training support. Authors also concludes that the master model they developed, along with additional modeling of the instances, entities, user perceptions, and other variables of interest, could be extended to a formal system model to be defined in future works.

Simulating cyber security management: A gamified approach to executive decision making

The paper investigates the importance of training for decision makers to empower them with the skills needed for preserving a secure environment. Authors present Aurelius, a cyber security simulation game specifically targeted for training executives to better understand the correlation of cyber security policies and business outcome, through the modelling of policies and simulation of their effects on organizations. The simulator leverages aspects of cyber security with players' deciding their investment strategy, while presenting them with real-time simulated consequences of their decision.

Artificial intelligence and machine learning in dynamic cyber risk analytics at the edge

In this paper, authors investigate how internet of things enables artificial intelligence (AI) advances in real-time processing, sensing and actuation between cyber physical systems and provide capabilities for system analysis of the cyber structures being considered. Authors presents a taxonomy with respect of the areas of focus identified in the literature on cyber risk analytics. The taxonomy details the requirements for predictive cyber risk analytics, in which AI components and connectors service the entire system during its operation. The paper reports a new framework explaining how AI can be integrated with cyber risk analytics, confirming that CPS design requires an understanding of system design, system engineering and system sociology.

Modelling cyber resilience in a water treatment and distribution system

The paper presents a novel cyber resilience assessment approach for critical infrastructure systems, which relies on stochastic simulation techniques. The methodology accounts for cyber-socio-technical perspectives on the complex systems under analysis, by modelling its functioning at different stages. As such, the methodology is instantiated in a water distribution system comprehending both a water treatment plant and a water distribution network serving citizens. The system is studied when disrupted by a successful cyber attack. Results show how the simulation-based methodology permits to assess resilience quantitatively, providing support for water sector managers against cyber threats.

Extending causal models from machines into humans

The paper shows how to combine separate technical and social causal models into an integrated socio-technical causal model. Major emerging challenges are represented by the difficulty in converting the human models into causal models due to the lack of detailed measures for the human behavior. Overall, authors point out that extending technical models with human models and use automatic tool to reason about these models is an essential building block for accountable CPS that are well integrated into societal context.

On Combining Domain Modeling and Organizational Modeling for Developing Adaptive Cyber-Physical Systems

In this paper authors investigate cyber physical systems from an organizational perspective. As such authors propose the integration of an architecture model (SGAM) with agent-oriented practices. Authors point out that this integration approach has multiple applications within the organization for CPS-development. Accordingly, the integrated model can be used for a static analysis of the system, the evaluation of what-if scenarios exploiting agent-based simulations, the optimization of the system adaptation by considering the model itself as a system element.

Route Choice-Based Socio-Technical Macroscopic Traffic Model

The paper proposes a socio-technical traffic model for vehicles. The proposed model captures the effect of human passengers' route choices by embedding a route choice attribute in a traffic flow model. The human passengers' choice of routes leads to a multi-class traffic system where each class of vehicles corresponds to each route. To validate the model, authors perform a case study for a particular driving cost function and present inherent simulation results. Furthermore, authors compare their model with an existing traffic model to motivate the significance of adopting the socio-technical perspective.

Systems Dynamics Modeling for Evaluating Socio-Technical Vulnerabilities in Advanced Persistent Threats

The paper investigates the application of System Dynamics modelling for simulating socio-technical vulnerabilities in complex and dynamic human-computer interaction settings. Authors simulate socio-technical variables of an advanced persistent threat (APT) attack on an organization using System Dynamics approach to visualize the interaction between system variables. Applying the simulation methodology on a case study related to a warehouse data breach, authors identify six socio variables and three technical variables that lead to the investigated disruption. The presented methodology can be used to evaluate what-if scenarios in light of successful cyber attacks.

A human-in-the-loop manufacturing control architecture for the next generation of production systems

The paper examines the possibility and advantages of relying on human-in-the-loop techniques for production system control. To this purpose, authors investigate existing taxonomies and models to elaborate a system architecture for Social Human-in-the-loop Cyber-Physical Production System. Authors state that technologies supporting physical capabilities of humans are particularly useful to enhance the sensing and actuation role of human operators. As such, the centrality of the operator becomes fundamental in the proposed architecture. The study enables an extensive and comprehensive understanding of the role of humans in the development of modern manufacturing systems with respect to decision making processes of smart factories.

HoS-ML: Socio-Technical System ADL Dedicated to Human Vulnerability Identification

This paper investigates the problem of detecting a human vulnerability in socio-technical systems. Authors identify human factors relevant to security aspects and then propose a human-oriented architecture description language in terms of operational connections between human operators, considering their factors. Moreover, Bayesian networks are finally used in the paper to simulate human vulnerabilities, considering the specified factors, and estimating their impact on the modeled socio-technical system.

A Framework for Improving Rural Microgrid Sustainability Through Integrated Socio-technical Considerations

This paper presents a framework for connecting life-quality (in terms of satisfaction of user demands) and sustainable power management to support decision making. The solutions are developed using the compromise decision support problem (cDSP), and the foundational mathematics on which the framework relies to define the cDSP is presented in the paper. The framework considers the relationships between the qualitative aspects of the social dynamics and the quantitative aspects of the technical system

ANNEX C – Information flow modelling papers details

In addition to the summary table of the most relevant paper adopting the information flow modelling approach. Annex C describes more details of each paper in which highlight and explain the overall research, the methodology to achieve the objectives and briefly the results obtained with a quick conclusion.

The Analysis of the Socio-Technical Environment (STE) of Online Sextortion Using Case Studies and Published Reports from a Cybersecurity Perspective

This comprehensive paper explores the STE of online sextortion, defining it as sexual exploitation involving abuse of power or threatened release of sexual content. Employing Checkland's Soft System Methodology and a modified EAST model, the study adopts a cybersecurity perspective to address the complex interrelationships between people, information, processes, and technology in online networks. It evaluates the impact of sextortion and examines the responses of law enforcement, governments, NGOs, and technology companies. The concept of cyber herd immunity is introduced, promoting security by default, encryption, access protection, whitelisting, malicious code prevention, and regular software updates. The paper underscores the intertwined socio-technical nature of online sextortion, advocating for a holistic approach in addressing both social engineering and technical vulnerabilities. Recommendations for future actions include holistic planning, the development of a cyber-deterrence strategy by law enforcement, enhanced digital evidence recording, expanded IP blocking, increased cooperation between stakeholders for cybersecurity education, active measures by technology companies using software and AI, encouragement of better personal security behavior through feedback applications, and the expansion of cyber insurance coverage for individuals. Overall, the paper provides a nuanced examination of the multifaceted issue of online sextortion and proposes actionable strategies for prevention and response across various domains.

An agent-based socio-technical approach to impact assessment for cyber defense

This paper introduces a groundbreaking simulation methodology designed to estimate the impact of cyber attacks, addressing shortcomings in current approaches that often focus on isolated aspects like assets or business processes. This is achieved through an agent-based socio-technical model that integrates both human and technological elements. The model's uniqueness lies in its ability to comprehensively analyze consequences across business processes, roles, and systems, offering a holistic understanding of the impact of cyber attacks. The primary focus is on providing situational awareness for cyber defense, with a specific application in critical information infrastructures. The paper discusses the existing methods developed for managing Information Systems Security (ISS) or Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA). The proposed model aims to overcome these limitations by focusing on impact rather than risk estimation, employing an agent-based socio-technical approach that captures the dynamic interactions between humans and technology within organizations. The model is characterized by its adaptability and scalability, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the complex evolution of events. It facilitates forward and backward chaining analyses to explore transitions between different states, enabling a more nuanced analysis of events, impact, dependencies, and risk mitigation strategies.

A Socio-Technical and Co-evolutionary Framework for Reducing Human-Related Risks in Cyber Security and Cybercrime Ecosystems

This paper challenges the traditional perspective on cybersecurity, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive socio-technical framework that goes beyond practical implementation. The proposed socio-technical framework is designed to provide a more nuanced understanding of human-related risks and support the development of effective approaches to engage individuals and organizations in risk reduction. The framework considers various human actors, including offenders, preventers, promoters, responders, and victims, in a closed-loop system. It aims to combine theories and data-driven analysis, creating a computational ontology and knowledge base for user-facing software tools and preventers-facing analytics.

Two specific use cases are outlined to demonstrate the applicability of the framework. The first involves understanding human behavior in a connected transport system to prevent cyber-physical crimes. This includes investigating the values and motivations influencing location-sharing behaviors of transport users, variations across different population segments, and the interplay of cyber-physical behaviors among users and offenders. The ultimate goal is to create a socio-technical framework that contributes to a more adaptive and holistic approach to cybersecurity, addressing the complex interplay between technical elements and human behaviors.

Modeling the Handling of Knowledge for Industry 4.0

The advent of Industry 4.0, characterized by the interconnection of cyber-physical systems in production and logistics, brings significant changes to the socio-technical system of factories. These changes include an increased demand for training due to the shortage of skilled workers, the opening of factory boundaries to third-party access, the merging of office IT and manufacturing IT, and a redefined understanding of machine data utilization. The paper addresses the need for an analysis and design method for knowledge management that integrates human and machine interactions in the Industry 4.0 era. It introduces KMDL3.0, an extended modeling language, as a tool to represent, analyze, and optimize knowledge processing with a focus on artificial intelligence and machine learning in both office and production environments. The language facilitates the quantification and evaluation of qualification characteristics, enabling the creation of personalized qualification plans. However, future versions of KMDL need to address questions related to knowledge aggregation, rules for aggregation, experimental validation of quantitative effects, and the impact of additional interactions with physical objects on knowledge objects.

Expertise, social influence, and knowledge aggregation in distributed information processing

The article presents a comprehensive investigation into knowledge aggregation in Distributed Information Processing (DIP) units within social, cyber-physical, and socio-technical systems. It introduces an algorithm rooted in Nowak's Regulatory Theory of Social Influence (RTSI) to address the challenge of self-organization in a distributed setting without centralized authority. The proposed approach is evaluated using a multi-agent simulator called SMARTSIS, applied to a scenario involving a linear public goods game and qualitative questions of distributive justice. The contributions of the article encompass three key aspects. Firstly, it offers a detailed formal specification of the algorithm based on the RTSI theory. Secondly, the algorithm is implemented in a multi-agent simulator, and the results of three experiments demonstrate how autonomous agents can effectively self-organize as a DIP unit using RTSI, ensuring knowledge aggregation and resource conservation. Lastly, the article explores the problem of knowledge aggregation in the context of reflective self-improvement over time, revealing how social influence processes can reconcile

conflicting systemic drivers. The article underscores the significance of theories like RTSI in enhancing the collective knowledge of diverse individuals within distributed systems.

*From Cyber Incidents to Training Cognitive Situation Management: *Work in Progress*

This paper represents the first outcomes of research that is still in progress. Authors attempt to apply a cognitive learning model in agent-based computational economics to create a comprehensive environment for cybersecurity situation modeling, reasoning and learning. This model aims to support human and/or computational understanding of situations. The study aims to design and develop a hand-on cybersecurity platform to train cognitive situation management in cyber ranges. This platform allows decision-makers context of cybersecurity, to explore the strategies that impact on the cybersecurity of the system as a whole, identify and evaluate threats, learn about their opponents and other players, and manage the complex and dynamic situations.

Social dimensions in cps & iot based automated production systems

The article deals with different human social dimensions associated with cyber physical systems and internet of things focusing on their conceptual evolution regarding automated production systems. The paper is a review that aims to take stock of current research trends to show the importance of integrating human operators as a part of a socio-technical system based autonomous and intelligent manufacturing systems. Consequently, three models of sociability as a way to integrate humans in future automated production systems have been identified from the literature and analyzed. The first model deals with the classical human-system interaction interfaces, where many works have been published to propose new interactive interfaces or embedded sensing systems. The second model aims to take advantage of the form of existing social network services (as social websites like Facebook) that offer a variety of features facilitating socialization based on the internet. The last model relates to the design of an industrial system as a society, linking smart connected objects through a typology of social relations.

A Socio-Technical Regime Transitions Model for Gerontechnology Service Design: Privacy, Information Security and Cyber Security in Focus

The purpose of this paper is to outline a socio-technical privacy, information security, and cyber security system modeling approach to support health care systems' aging in place. As such, authors are in the preliminary stage of the development of games and exercises in the Norwegian Cyber Range. Preliminary data collected from students experiencing these exercises has shown favorable results, but more data is needed to evaluate the learning outcomes.

InCReASE: A Dynamic Framework Towards Enhancing Situational Awareness in Cyber Incident Response

This study examines cybersecurity operations and incident response, and looks at how situation awareness knowledge is constructed through the organizational levels of enterprises when a cyber incident occurs. As such, this work contributes to situational awareness theory in the context of cybersecurity operations and incident response. Authors introduce InCReASE, a dynamic framework for enhancing situation awareness in Security Operations Centers during their operations and incident response. The framework relies on existing situational awareness models, combining elements of the existing body of knowledge and additional empirical findings by authors. The InCReASE framework models communication behavior and information flows between cybersecurity stakeholders to

coordinate the management of cybersecurity operations. Following the ‘Situation awareness cycle’ it is possible to projects the state of the socio-technical system and how it influences the operations.

The “Transparency for Safety” Triangle: Developing a Smart Transparency Framework to Achieve a Safety Learning Community

Authors conduct a literature on transparency and information sharing in health and safety based on the premise that if safety information is not sufficiently shared, people and the environment can be harmed. The findings show that such transparency as a subject highly present in the literature but the exchange of information is far from complete in practice. As such, the authors propose a sort of transparency standard, to study cyber-socio-technical systems safety. The constructed framework maps the health and safety information flows and supports their transparency to be located, assessed and improved. The framework add a societal domain extension to the holistic TEAM safety culture model, which connects organizations’ internal aspects of safety and their mutual relations. The resulting model includes three main stakeholders, i.e., people, organizations and government. The paper also analyzes the transparency needs of each stakeholder and delineates best practices to pursue such transparency.